

From Improvement to Development - the Challenges before School and the Role of Transformational Leadership to Encounter with

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ABSTRACT : The process of globalization, liberalization and privatization has brought a remarkable change in our society. Reformation movement has touched every component of present day society and civilization. The school where formal education at base level of our children occurs is not an exception. The school, under reformation process has to walk across the way from improvement to development by facing some challenges and it requires a leader who can be the torch bearer on this way. This paper tries to identify the challenges, those the school has to face for development and the necessity of leadership in school to face the challenges. It also tries to explore role of a head teacher as transformational leader and the strategies to be practiced to lead the school towards development.

Keywords : Challenges for development, transformational leadership.

Introduction

After the Second World War, the process of educating people has been facing changes from decade to decade. The World Leaders are showing their concern about the process of education. Naturally educational endeavors have become more extensive. Continuous rethinking is being done for redefining and reviewing of education in terms of concept, meaning, aims and objectives and process of

education which are carried out by different committees and commissions at national as well as international level. The world civilization is always proceeding towards better configuration riding on the boat of progress with its sailor as the knowledge society. New, wide-ranging, improved, diversified knowledge has touched every sphere of life leading to betterment. Significant reflection is being seen also in the school environment all over the world. The

dynamism, modernity and complexity in educational endeavor are imposing prominent changes over the environment of a school. The challenges from changing environment are demanding a new leadership quality, belief and competence from the head teacher so that he/she can take his/her institution through the process of development. In this regard the Transformational Leadership has been emerged as an evident part for leading a school from improvement phase to development phase which must be obligatory to every head teacher of schools.

Towards School Development:

The processes of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization have changed our society so abruptly that we are bound to change our whole gamut of education for survival as the fittest. In this age of knowledge-driven civilization, the aim of education is now multifaceted; educational process is more demanding; educational tasks are more difficult; expectations from the society are higher and diversified; inputs to the quality of teachers and the students are wide ranging and school accountability to the society and to the nation is greater than ever. As a result, educational policies, curriculum, teaching methods, organization and management of institutions demand changes and require to be modernized. The school comes first, which faces the increased challenges and requires prime attention for change. The school should start its journey from improvement to development as Cheng (1996) argues that there is a shift from traditional remedial concept of 'school improvement' to the challenging formative concept of 'school development'. For the purpose of 'development', school has to be active giving more emphasis on the challenge

areas than traditional areas. To look forward from improvement to development, school's challenges are:-

1. The Challenge of Change :

To ensure students' development and learning, especially during statutory schooling, traditionally, stability in the environment of school is strived for. Due to rapid societal changes, many educational changes need to be implemented in school. Yelland (2007) says, '... contemporary education system both at the national and local levels, are slowly beginning to realize that we need to create new context for learning that are relevant and meaningful and which prepare students for new times" (p-22). In new educational context, a school can not be luxurious in closing down, rethinks and restarts to by pass the changes. Instead of maintaining stability, school has to accept the challenge of changes in response to the pressures from society. (Middlewood, 1998).

2. Challenge of Quality:

Quantity is meant to reach education to children but quality is meant to prepare the children for future or for adulthood. School's existence is to satisfy needs of the species to survive and it exists because parents want their children to be the fittest survivors (Kapur, 2007). School must take responsibility to maintain the quality. People are more conscious and concerned about the quality of education than the quantity of education that school provides. The school authority should be concerned about whether school education meets high and diverse expectation of society, whether it can prepare children properly for future life. Naturally school has to emphasize on maintaining

and enhancing quality rather than expanding quantity of education.

3. Challenge of Effectiveness :

It is generally seen that the community is more concerned about the problems occurring in schools and school authority tries to solve the problems and retain normal functioning of school. Along with the normality of school functioning, it is essential to judge and to be alert about the effectiveness of school functioning. Effectiveness in school is one step ahead of ordinariness of school. Effective school can empower students with education of excellence. The school should take the challenge of maintaining its effectiveness to serve varied educational needs of the community.

4. Challenge of Autonomy:

According to Hoyle and Wallace (2005), “A major difficulty lies in the contextual diversity of schools and classrooms, which affects what works effectively in them. It is not possible reliably to specify from a central administrative level precisely what will work in individual school” (p-131). Traditional control from the apex body in a diversified context often restricts the practice of innovation in school and classroom management. Its main focus is to impose direction and restriction on the school authority for management. The control from the outside of school naturally ignores the needs of the community at base level as well as local level and found to be ineffective. Hoyle and Wallace (2005) argue, “Centralized reform runs the risk of using yesterday’s teaching techniques, developed in yesterday’s environment, to prepare today’s students for living and working in tomorrow’s world” (p-131). True decentralization of power or power of control

and reform within the school (i.e. autonomy of school) helps the authority on school based management working at the community needs and prepares students for better future. The school should take challenge of receiving and holding autonomy for the sake of positive change & effectiveness.

5. Challenge of Developing Potential:

According to Kapur (2007), “The process of learning should be such that it hones this potential in all students and ensures that this process of honing leads to the growth of the students”(P-5). The school is not merely a place of teaching some subjects to get promoted from one class to the upper. If the school authority claims that its way of teaching and preparing students is in a unique manner and that makes a difference with the others in the result of public examination that does not match with present day context of school purpose. The call of present time ‘Teach well to fit well’ signifies that the purpose of school is not only to prepare for public examination but also to develop potential of the learner and to develop their abilities to make them a complete citizen. The school should be so organized that every staff member takes the challenge of developing potential within the learner.

6. Challenge of Educational Technology:

If the goals of school are simple and controlled by the central authority, schools can be maintained by using simple techniques of management and can impart lessons through traditional methods of teaching. But as the role of schools are becoming more complex in accordance with the global perspective, the school should shift its focus toward using various innovations in educational technology, both

hardware & software, so that it can run school according to the global tradition. For the development of school, it is imperative for the school to address the challenge of using educational technology to introduce newness in teaching learning process.

7. Challenge of Self-evaluation:

If the assessment of school is done by district or central authority (inspectorate or directorate) or by any external agency obviously that will be done according to the norm and standard set by them. To make the school self supported in terms control and successful in terms of attainment, self evaluation of both the process and product of the school should be emphasized and carried out frequently giving importance - on the purposes for which it has been established, needs of parents for which they send their children to school.

These challenges together create the trends of reformation of educational process as well as school. To respond these trends of educational reforms and changes, there is a strong need of a school leadership that can initiate and facilitate transformation and development in school (Cheng, 1997). To initiate journey from improvement towards development of school; these challenges are to be encountered. The global perspective has initiated the movement of changing the school through reformation process. The changing environment of school inevitably requires such a person who can lead his school in the pursuit of quality enhancement. To meet the challenge of effectiveness, school needs such a leader who can transform his school which is effectiveness oriented. To meet the challenge of autonomy, the school requires such a leader who can motivate his staff to hold it. To meet the challenge of developing potential

within the students, school requires such a leader who sustains potentiality within him as well as his staff. To address the challenges of adopting technology, school requires such a leader who prepares himself as well as his staff ready for adopting technology. To meet the challenge of self evaluation, school requires such a leader who develops introspection in time.

What do we require in school - Management or Leadership?

The head teacher may function as an administrator or as a manager or as a leader. Mukhopadhyay (2004) says, "Administrators manage rules, regulations and protocols. Managers manage tasks and people. Leaders manage dreams and visions" (p-35). Head teacher as administrator has to work within limited space to follow only rules and regulations set by the controlling authority is in no way desirable in the school in this changing world. Stewart (2006) opines that 'leading and managing effective schools to respond to the increasingly complex demands of society will require the knowledge and technical skills of committed and competent leaders' (p-3). His role as a leader is little bit different from manager. Bolam (1999) defines "educational management as an executive function for carrying out agreed policy" (P-194). Sapre (2002) states, "Management is a set of activities directed towards efficient and effective utilization of organizational resources in order to achieve organizational goals" (P-102). These clearly state that management in school clearly accept the authority and control by central body who sets policy, rules, norms, standard for school and school's head teacher will assume the role of manager and take the responsibility to carry out several activities to achieve already set

standard. Cuban (1988) declares that management is linked with maintenance activity and leadership is linked with change. According to him, leadership is influencing other's actions in achieving desirable ends and leaders shape the goals, motivation, and actions of others. Egan (1988) argues that leaders make new things happen while managers keep things going in the direction set by leaders. "Leadership and management are seen equally necessary to innovate and to run organization. But leadership has a logical primacy over management when it comes to generating improvement" (Hoyle and Wallace, 2005, p-132). Management in school is not enough to make major innovation in practice for development. This is where leadership comes in which helps the new things made to happen. 'The greater the improvement sought, the more things made to happen, more leadership is needed' (ibid, p-132). So, leadership by a head teacher in school is more than management and a mean of ensuring better performance through innovation for transforming the school culture and environment. If a head teacher does not lead his/her institution well then 'a non leader as head of an institution spells its doom, the beginning of the end of the organizational decay" (Mukhopadhyay, 2004, p-36).

Transformational Leadership in School:-

To develop a school, the role of a head teacher is very significant. The studies on the topic of educational leadership suggest that in the past, head teachers were able to succeed, at least partially, by simply carrying out the directives of central authority by performing as a manager (Perez et al. 1999). But to meet new educational challenges, instead of assuming a managerial role, headmaster should play such

leadership role which envisions goals, sets standards, and communicates expectations to all stake holders of school in such a way that all concerned directly or indirectly know where the school is going and what is the purpose of its existence in the community (Drake and Roe, 1999). The mode of action of head teacher should create a belief for development, establish an environment to work better for teacher and help the students to know more & develop potential for future.

Bass (1985) contends that there is a continuum of leadership in which laissez-fair leadership stands on one extreme point which has hands-off approach. Next is transactional leadership in which leaders create situation where doing what leaders desire is in the self-interest of followers. At another extreme point, there exists transformational leadership in which leaders encourage followers to reach beyond their self interest to embrace a collective goal advocated by leaders. The concept and development of the notion of transformational leadership are associated with James McGregor Burns, Bernard M. Bass, J. Avolio and Kenneth Leithwood. The idea of transformational leadership was first developed by James McGregor Burns in 1978 and later extended by Bernard M. Bass as well as others. Burns(1978) opines that transformational leadership occurs when one or more persons engage with one another and they increase level of motivation and morality and this leadership seeks to 'raise the level of human conduct and ethical aspiration of both the leader and led, and thus it has a transforming effect on both' (ibid, P-20). To describe transformational leadership, Leithwood, Jantzi and Steinbach (1999) declare:

This form of leadership assumes that the

central focus of leadership ought to be the commitments and capacities of organizational members. Higher levels of personal commitment to organizational goals and greater capacities for accomplishing those goals are assumed to result in extra effort and greater productivity. (p.9)

In an organization like school, “Transformational leadership is more potent and complex and occurs when one or more teachers engage with others in such a way that administrators and teachers raise one another to higher levels of commitment and dedication, motivation and morality.” (Miller and Miller, 2001, p.182). In case of a school it may be mentioned that “Through the transforming process, the motives of the leader and the follower merge” (ibid, p.182).

The components of Transformational leadership:-

Bass (1998) identifies the components (the four ‘I’s) of transformational leadership which are further measured with the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ). The following four are the components of transformational leadership-

- (i) Idealized Influence: - Idealized influence is envisioning, confident and sets high standard for emulation.
- (ii) Inspirational Motivation: – inspirational motivation provides followers with challenges and meaning for engaging in shared goals and undertakings.
- (iii) Intellectual Stimulation: – Intellectual stimulation helps followers to question assumptions and generate more creative solutions to problems.

- (iv) Individualized Consideration: – Individualized consideration treats each follower as an individual and provides coaching, mentoring and growth opportunities.

Expectations from a head teacher as transformational leader:-

Liontos (1992) describes that Leithwood finds transformational leaders help staff to develop and maintain a collaborative, professional school culture. This means staff members often talk, observe, critique, and plan together. Norms of collective responsibility and continuous improvement encourage them to teach each other how to teach better. Transformational leaders involve staff in collaborative goal setting, reduce teacher isolation, use bureaucratic mechanisms to support cultural changes, share leadership with others by delegating power, and actively communicate the school’s norms and beliefs. Teachers’ aspirations for professional growth motivate them for development. This process is facilitated when teachers are strongly committed to a school mission. Leithwood finds that transformational leaders help teachers to solve problems more effectively and stimulates teachers to engage in new activities and put forth extra effort. Transformational leaders use practices primarily to help staff members work smarter, not harder and shared a genuine belief of working together with staff members could develop better solutions.

The head teacher of a school can change the school environment and show the way of development by his/her leadership. As a transformational leader he/she will have a clear vision and purpose of his/her school and confidence in taking risk to provide foundation

for organizational changes. He/she has to motivate others, generate enthusiasm to challenge obstacles. It is necessary for him/her to communicate expectation and demonstrate commitment to goals and shared vision. The Head teacher must encourage his/her colleagues to imagine and to contribute to the attractive development of school. For this purpose, he/she has to seek new ideas and adopt innovations and stimulate others to be creative. He/she has to raise the capacity and standard of his/her staff to make them sensitive to problems and solve the problems with fullest endeavor. Head teacher should assume such role which sends the message that he/she is aware of individual concerns i.e. specific, unique needs of his/her staff. He/she has to establish such environment in school that every individual feels- well-treated, supported and allowed to reach higher levels of achievement and develop according to his/her talent & knowledge. He/she must demonstrate high performance expectation and create a productive school culture that helps students to learn. The Head teacher as a leader has to model best practices and inculcate positive organizational values.

What Strategies can be adopted by a head teacher as a transformational leader?

Here are additions and alterations to the specific ideas, culled from several sources (Liontos, Cheng, Gray and Streshly) on transformational leadership that a head teacher can adopt and practice to lead school development:

1. Involve the whole staff in deliberating on visions, school goals and beliefs at the beginning of the year.
2. Build and improve relationship with

each person with whom interaction occurs- teachers, students, parents and other people who are engaged in school process and contribute in any way for school development.

3. Assist in classrooms and encourage teachers to visit one another's classes.
4. Assist teachers to plan and prepare lessons for teaching.
5. Visit each (if possible) classroom every day.
6. Help teachers work smarter by actively seeking different interpretations and checking out assumptions; place individual problems in the larger perspective of the whole school;
8. Avoid commitment to preconceived solutions;
9. Clarify and summarize the key points during meetings; and keep the group on assignment but not to impose own perspective.
10. Use action research teams as a way of sharing power.
11. Conduct action research for finding the gaps between executed effort and achievement.
12. Give everyone responsibilities and involve staff in governance functions.
13. Give charge of a committee to the non participating members and review its work regularly for creating enthusiasm.
14. Find the good things that are happening and publicly recognize the work of staff and students who have contributed to school development.

15. Write private notes to teachers expressing appreciation for special efforts.
16. Survey the wants and needs of staff.
17. Let the staff know that head teacher is receptive to teachers' attitudes, beliefs and philosophies.
18. Use active listening and show people that the head teacher truly cares about them.
19. Let teachers experiment with new ideas.
20. Share and discuss research with teachers. Propose questions for teachers to think about.
21. Bring workshops to the school for staff to participate or send the teachers to workshop / seminar according to suitability.
22. Get teachers to share their talents with one another.
23. Give a workshop / seminar and share information with staff on conferences / seminars that is attended. Follow the same for other staff.
24. When hiring new staff, let them know, the head teacher want them actively involved in school decision-making.
25. Invite expert teachers with a commitment to collaboration. Give teachers the option to transfer if they can't wholly commit themselves to the school's purposes.
26. Demonstrate high expectations for teachers and students. Tell teachers that the headmaster want them to be the best teacher and student the best performer.
27. Use bureaucratic mechanisms to support teachers, such as finding money for a project or providing time for collaborative planning during the workday.
28. Protect teachers from the problems of limited time, excessive paperwork, and demands from other agencies.
29. Let the teachers know that they are responsible for all students, not just their own classes.
30. Help the members to identify strength and weaknesses of school's educational process and assess the educational needs of students and the developmental needs of teachers.
31. Maximize opportunities for student learning and staff development through appropriate structuring of work and manpower.
32. Encourage members to link up monitoring and evaluating process to the educational process and established instructional goal and use the educational indicators to monitor and develop teaching process and educational outcome.
33. Encourage teachers to be updated with new knowledge of educational technology and innovations in teaching learning practice.
34. Give confidence to the teachers for improvisation in teaching learning process.

35. Review the progress of workload of staff at the end of week / fortnight
36. Develop a good library of resources to get the updated knowledge.

Conclusion

Now it is the time to collectively reconsider and determine the purpose of school in the community and make changes for the positive impact of student learning and achievement for the survival of the fittest and largely school effectiveness under the backdrop of globalization. School should be given freedom from every corner to support the head teacher's needs to work as a transformational leader. To create a new perspective in school environment, the head teacher can be a transformational leader and he/she can make the school a vibrant one in terms of vision and mission building, process practicing, goal achieving and productive citizen creating. Transformational leadership in school by the head teacher can bring beneficial changes in the school culture and in the process of teaching-learning leading to a qualitative and sustained development in performance arising out of enhanced motivation and commitment of the staff. This type of leadership provides the zeal to increase the commitment to the goal of the school and to motivate staff to perform at their best for the sake of the pupils, colleagues as well as for the development of school. Transformational leadership helps in fostering vision building, individual support, intellectual stimulation, modeling, culture creating and holding high performance expectation that leads school effectiveness and development. It is the reality in the modern world that the educational arena is driven by social, economical, technological and political changes and the school has no choice of defending these rather

to cope with the changes for the development and preparation of our future citizen. We require now a transformational leader who can transform the school vision and mission oriented and committed to accomplish the same.

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